

Towards a Modular Infrastructure for Comprehensive RDM¹

Idea for a TDCC SSH Challenge Project²

Frans Oort, Eva Lekkerkerker, Emma Schreurs, Tako Horsley³

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Dutch universities have policies or guidelines for RDM in the SSH domain.⁴ However, not all universities have the complete infrastructure required for full implementation of RDM policies, including FAIR data policies. To ensure compliance with applicable laws, regulations and institutional policies, it is important that infrastructure is appropriate, compliant and easy to use, freeing researchers from administrative tasks, reducing the workload of support staff and providing accurate management information.

A comprehensive RDM infrastructure would potentially consist of (at least) the following components: (1) temporary workspace storage, (2) closed storage for archiving (raw, sensitive) data, (3) publication platform for publishing data, (4) a 'research data exchange' (RDX)⁵ or 'data access broker' (DAB)⁶ for conditional data sharing in a responsible manner, subject to agreement to 'terms of use', (5) a secure workspace for analysis of (sensitive) data enabled by a 'trusted research environment' (TRE)⁷, such as SANE⁸, (6) a 'FAIR data hub' (FDH)⁹ for transferring data to either a closed archive or an open publication platform, including essential metadata, (7) supporting data management software, such as Yoda/ iRODS¹⁰, (8) a research registration portal for ethics reviews, data management plans, project control, archiving and publication of data, etc., with automated support and workflows to reduce the burden on both researchers and support staff, and (9) a user-friendly interface that enables researchers and support staff to easily access and navigate all components. The three types of storage are illustrated in Figure 1 (next page).

At present, universities are independently developing similar services on a small scale. Individual universities have limited capacity. We want to explore which infrastructure components are of common interest, so that we can make the development of the infrastructure a joint effort. As not all universities will be interested in all or the same components, this infrastructure should be modular, so that universities can pick and choose the components they want to include in their own (local) infrastructure.

We propose to (1) explore the extent to which universities share the same RDM policies and need similar infrastructure with similar components, (2) make an inventory of infrastructure components (storage, tools, services) currently available and in use, (3) perform a fit-gap analysis to evaluate existing components and identify those that already fit, those that need

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² Dutch grant programme: <https://tdcc.nl/nwo-tdcc-call-2023/tdcc-ssh-project-development-process/>

³ Contact addresses: f.j.oort@uva.nl, e.lekkerkerker@uva.nl, e.e.schreurs@uva.nl t.m.horsley@uva.nl

⁴ For an example of general RDM policy principles see <https://zenodo.org/records/10954657>

⁵ For a short explanation of the RDX see <https://zenodo.org/records/8269273> or the AMDEX website

⁶ For a short explanation of the DAB see <https://dab.surf.nl/about/>

⁷ For an explanation of TRE see <https://zenodo.org/record/4594704#.Ys7RuHZBzIU>

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.4594703>

⁸ For a short explanation of SANE see <https://www.surf.nl/en/themes/research-infrastructure/sane-secure-environment-for-analysing-sensitive-data>

⁹ For a short description of the FDH see <https://zenodo.org/records/11201003>

¹⁰ For a short explanation of Yoda/ iRODS see <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/yoda-hosting>

further development, and those that need new development, and (4) produce an action plan for establishing a modular infrastructure for comprehensive RDM.

Figure 1: Workspace storage, archiving, and publication of data in separate locations.

Note: Temporary storage will be provided as WORKSPACE storage for data processing and analysis, for the duration of the research project. Immediately after data collection, and at any other appropriate time, the researcher will submit data packages for archiving. The ARCHIVE stores data packages with full provenance for an indefinite period, closed, accessible only after approval by the Dean. Data packages suitable for publication are submitted to the PUBLICATION PLATFORM, which holds data packages for an indefinite period, open, but subject to use conditions, regulated by the Research Data Exchange (RDX).